

IMPACT OF GLOBAL COMPETITION ON THE FORMATION OF AIRLINE BUSINESS MODELS

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For more than 100 years, the air transportation industry has marked a new era of a fundamentally new stage in the development of mankind - an era of unlimited possibilities. Literally in 24 hours you can reach any point on the planet. Without air travel it is already impossible to imagine the existence of a modern person, business and the state. Previously, air travel was considered the privilege of the rich, not many could afford such a luxury. On board the aircraft, passengers were provided with many different services, and before and after the flight they could relax in comfortable lounges.

This is how the classic business model of air carriers appeared, which, in addition to the flight itself, implies a large number of additional services. In 1973, after the oil embargo, it became clear that it would be extremely difficult for airlines to survive in an environment of volatile and high oil prices, since aviation fuel derived from it is a major cost component. This circumstance gave impetus to the development of the budget business model.

The emergence of new types of aircraft that use less fuel, fly longer distances and provide better passenger comfort has made transportation more common. New low-cost air carriers were emerging, which ensured high competition for the already existing classical air

carriers. The industry entered a mature stage in the late 1990s and early 2000s, characterized by more M&A deals, rising promotional costs, and an increased focus on service and, most importantly, cost.

Competition has created differences in business models, which in turn create competitive advantages. From its inception, the airline industry has been capital-intensive on the one hand, and on the other hand, air carriers must keep ticket prices affordable in order to maintain and increase demand.

It is known that the theory and practice of modern strategic management identifies three basic approaches to the conduct of competition: cost advantage, differentiation and focusing. Accordingly, these approaches should be adapted to the type of business model of the airline. The solution of this problem is recommended to be carried out taking into account the impact of the following new trends in the development of the air transport business:

1. In the structure of aviation holdings, air transportation remains the main activity in terms of income;

2. The world's leading airlines are actively developing hybrid business models of air transportation, characterized as follows:

- Former full-service airlines: increase fare elasticity, offer lower base fares, promote direct sales, reduce free catering levels, reduce ground turnaround times to less than 45 minutes, use aggressive marketing policies, increase all types of productivity;

- Former low-cost airlines: provision of seat reservation service, provision of catering at no additional charge, provision of audio and video on board aircraft, provision of PLP programs, differentiation of

services at an additional cost, cooperation with tour operators and agents.

These trends lead to the emergence of new types of competitive advantages, which provide the basis for choosing a competitive strategy and achieving competitiveness of AC in the long run.

When evaluating the intensity of market competition, it must be taken into account that different business models of airlines, as a rule, do not compete with each other. At the same time, most airlines currently operate under a mixed model, which means that the only competitive advantage they can offer the passenger is the price of the ticket. Such competition deprives aircraft carriers of many opportunities, for example, renewal of the aircraft fleet, which may ultimately lead to exit from the market as the resource of the existing fleet is depleted.

So, in honor of the celebration of the 30th anniversary of the Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as in pursuance of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5100 dated April 30, 2021, Uzbekistan Airways JSC switched to a hybrid model of air transportation and on August 30, 2021 the first flight was made to Tashkent - Moscow.

Uzbekistan Express will focus on intra-republican and inter-regional transportation and will start air transportation on 4 Airbus A320 aircraft arranged in "full economy". The future air route map will also include key cities such as Moscow, Novosibirsk, Kazan, Rostov-on-Don, Krasnodar, Sochi, Mineralnye Vody, Yekaterinburg, Aktau and Aktobe.

Conclusion: Thus, having considered the different types of airline business models and their characteristics, we come to the conclusion that in an intense market competition it is very important to consider how airlines change their business models as part of their strategy. In order to track these changes, it is necessary to study the tools for analyzing the external and internal environment of airlines.

At the same time, the development of a strategy for each business model should be carried out taking into account the following recommendations:

- Different business models of airlines do not compete with each other, they operate in different types of competitive markets and have different types of competitive advantages;

- Achieving competitive advantages in the market involves maximum adaptation of the structure of the aircraft fleet and the airline's route network to the type of business model used;

- The requirements of customers of various business models of airlines have significant differences in the field of price and quality indicators of the competitiveness of their products. The practical use of these recommendations by airline management will help to avoid erroneous decisions in the field of implementing a competitive strategy in the conditions of the modern air transport market.

REFERENCES:

1. Raqamli iqtisodiyot va elektron hukumatni keng joriy etish choratadbirlari to'g'risida" 2020 yil 28 apreldagi PQ-4699-son qarori
2. Shodiyeva, G., Tog'ayeva, D. A., & Sul'tonov, B. A. (2022). KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O'RNINI. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(5), 610-613.

3. Mardievna, S. G., & Oblokulovich, K. S. Methodology for Determining the Role of Family Business in the Economy.
4. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ИННОВАЦИОН РИВОЖЛАНИШ МОДЕЛЛАРИ ВА УЛАРНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ ЎСИШ БИЛАН АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 17(1), 101-105.
5. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT MODELS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC GROWTH. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(10), 662-665.
6. Shakirova, F. B. (2022). ТЕМИР ЙЎЛ ТРАНСПОРТИ СОҲАСИДАГИ ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЧИЛИК МУНОСАБАТЛАРИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 16(3), 82-85.
7. Шакирова, Ф. Б. (2022). ТРАНСПОРТ СОҲАСИДА ДАВЛАТ-ХУСУСИЙ ШЕРИКЛИК МЕХАНИЗМЛАРИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШНИНГ ХОРИЖИ ТАЖРИБАСИ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 15(3), 66-74.
8. Shakirova, F. B., & Sattorova, S. B. (2022). “О ‘ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO ‘LLARI” AJ FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO HAMKORLIK FAOLIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(9), 4-9.
9. Shakirova, F. B. (2015). Development of Economy in Uzbekistan on the Basis of Innovation Activity (Uzbekistan, Tashkent). *Problems of Modern Economics*, (3), 55.
10. Mardiyevna, S. G., & Anvarovna, E. D. (2022). MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF FAMILY BUSINESSES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 206-211.
11. Shadieva, G. M., & o‘g‘li Isoqulov, Z. S. (2022). WAYS TO REDUCE POVERTY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 957-962.

12. Рахманбаева, Р. А. (2012). Управление интеллектуальным потенциалом вузов в условиях интеграции образования и производства. *Автореф. дисс.... д-ра эконом. наук.*

13. Рахманбаева, Р. А. (2020). Главный фактор развития новой экономики постиндустриального общества. *Журнал PalArch по археологии Египта/египтологии, 17(6), 14201-14207.*